

Factors Affecting Identity and Entrepreneurship¹

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Abstract: The aim of this research is to reveal the effects of factors such as age, gender, and education on identity characteristics and entrepreneurship orientation. The research universe consists of employees working in the central district of Tokat. The "Entrepreneurial Orientation Scale" and "Identity Scale" were used to collect the data to be used in the research. A questionnaire was prepared to measure demographic factors. The analysis results show that entrepreneurship orientation does not differ according to any demographic factor. When personal identity is examined, it is determined that the averages of those who are younger than older, women than men, and singles than married are higher. In terms of the length of time working in the current job and workplace, the personal identity averages of those who have worked for more years are lower. When social identity is examined, it is revealed that the averages of women are higher than men and those who work as personnel at the workplace are higher than those who are bosses. The collective identity average is lower at older ages. Multiple regression analysis was conducted to determine the effect of demographic factors on identity and entrepreneurship. However, the analysis results were not found to be statistically significant.

Keywords: Gender, Marital Status, Personal Identity, Social Identity, Collective Identity

1. Introduction

Entrepreneurial orientation can be defined as the processes and activities undertaken to start a new business (Ercan & Yıldırım, 2021). Identity, on the other hand, is individuals' views of who they are (Coşkun, 2004). It is believed that an employee's view of who they are will vary depending on characteristics such as age, gender, education level, whether they are the owner or employee of the business, and length of time at the job and in the workplace. Furthermore, these demographic factors are expected to influence employees' entrepreneurial orientations. The entrepreneurial orientation scale used to collect the research data includes three dimensions: risk taking, innovation, and proactivity; the identity scale includes three factors: personal, social, and collective. The purpose of this research is to reveal the impact of employees' demographic characteristics on both their identity and entrepreneurial orientation. Furthermore, the research will examine whether identity and entrepreneurial orientation differ according to demographic factors.

2. Conceptual Framework

Identity is defined as "the totality of signs, qualities, and characteristics that indicate what kind of person one is as a social being." While often used interchangeably, the concepts of identity and personality exhibit distinct characteristics. Güvenç (1993) defines personality as a person's unique behavioral characteristics, emphasizing that it is objective and externally visible; identity, on the other hand, is how a person perceives themselves and with whom they identify. While personality is a widely researched topic in organizational behavior, research on identity is limited. Therefore, this study focused on employee identity factors.

Identity was measured using three different dimensions in the study. In the personal identity subscale, individuals were asked to rate unique elements such as their values, dreams, goals, feelings, thoughts, and concerns. In the social identity subscale, individuals were asked whether they considered characteristics that could be evaluated by others, such as height, weight, attractiveness, gestures, and style, important. In the collective identity dimension, individuals were asked to rate elements such as ethnicity, religion,

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region, country, and interest in political issues. Entrepreneurial individuals perceive opportunities in their environment and desire to create economic value from them (Ercan & Yıldırım, 2021). Entrepreneurial individuals are individuals with distinctive characteristics who are open to innovation and willing to take risks. Consequently, the entrepreneurship scale in this study consists of the sub-dimensions of risk-taking, innovation, and proactivity. Risk-taking involves acting boldly in unfamiliar situations and investing time and money in these endeavors. Innovation means that an individual goes beyond the norm and tries unique methods. Proactivity, on the other hand, is preferring to create plans that others will follow rather than following others. All printed material, including text, illustrations, and charts, must be kept within the parameters of the 8 15/16-inch (53.75 picas) column length and 5 15/16-inch (36 picas) column width. Please do not write or print outside of the column parameters. Margins are 3.3cm on the left side, 3.65cm on the right, 2.03cm on the top, and 3.05cm on the bottom. Paper orientation in all pages should be in portrait style.

3. Research Method

The purpose of the study was to determine whether demographic characteristics influence identity factors and entrepreneurial orientation. To achieve this goal, data was collected from 60 employees. The research was conducted using a survey design.

3.1. Population and Sample

The research population consisted of workplace employees in the central district of Tokat. Convenience sampling, a non-probability sampling method, was used as the sampling technique. Convenience sampling is a sampling technique in which everyone who can be reached—that is, everyone who responds to the survey—is included in the sample (Gürbüz & Şahin, 2016: 134).

3.2. Data Collection Tools

The first part of the data collection tool contains nine questions to identify demographic factors such as age, gender, marital status, and education. The second part includes the entrepreneurial orientation scale, developed by Bolton and Lane (2012), consisting of 10 statements and three dimensions. The third and final section includes the identity scale, originally developed by Cheek and Briggs (1982) but later supplemented with new items and dimensions by researchers, and validated in a Turkish sample by Coşkun (2004). The entrepreneurial orientation scale includes three dimensions: risk taking (items 1, 2, and 3), innovativeness (items 4, 5, 6, and 7), and proactivity (items 8, 9, and 10). The identity scale includes three factors: personal (items 1, 4, 7, 10, 13, 15, 16, 17, 20, and 23), social (items 2, 5, 8, 11, 14, 18, and 21), and collective (items 3, 6, 9, 12, 19, 22, 24, and 25). Responses to the statements in the entrepreneurship orientation scale were evaluated as "1 = Strongly Disagree," "2 = Disagree," "3 = Neither Agree nor Disagree," "4 = Agree," and "5 = Strongly Agree." Responses to the statements in the identity scale were evaluated as "Not Important," "Rarely Important," "Usually Important," "Very Important," and "Always Very Important."

3.3. Pre-Analysis Procedures

Before data analysis, frequency analysis was first conducted to check for incorrect definitions and data. Any errors detected were corrected. The data was then checked for normal distribution. According to George and Mallery (2003), skewness and kurtosis values between -1.5 and +1.5, and according to Tabachnick and Fidell (2020), skewness and kurtosis values between -2 and +2 indicate a normal distribution of the data. The analysis results indicate a normal distribution of the data.

3.4. Scale Reliability Analyses

Cronbach's alpha values were calculated to determine the internal consistency reliability of the scales. Reliability coefficients were examined for both the overall scale and the individual subscales. Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the scales and their subscales are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Reliability Coefficients of Scales

	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient
Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.74
Risk Taking	0.71
Innovation	0.54
Proactivity	0.41
Identity	0.83
Personal Identity	0.77
Social Identity	0.78
Collective Identity	0.59

In exploratory studies, a Cronbach's alpha value of up to 0.50 can be considered reasonable (Altunışık et al., 2004:115). The reliability of the entrepreneurial orientation and identity scales is understood to be sufficient. Reliability coefficients for all subscales, except for the "proactivity" subscale, are within acceptable limits.

4. Findings

SPSS was used for data analysis. First, a correlation analysis was conducted to identify the relationships between demographic variables and entrepreneurship and identity. Table 2 displays the analysis results. The correlation analysis results reveal no significant relationship between the entrepreneurship and collective identity variables and demographic factors. An examination of the personal identity variable revealed a negative correlation with age, gender, and tenure at work and at work, and a positive correlation with marital status. There were also negative and significant relationships between social identity and gender and workplace role. Accordingly, variables with significant relationships tend to co-vary. In exploratory studies, a Cronbach's alpha value of up to 0.50 can be considered reasonable (Altunışık et al., 2004:115). The reliability of the entrepreneurial orientation and identity scales is understood to be sufficient. Reliability coefficients for all subscales, except for the "proactivity" subscale, are within acceptable limits.

Table 2: Results of Correlation Analysis Between Variables

	Entrepreneurship	Personal Identity	Social Identity	Collective Identity
1. Age	0.006	-0.293*	-0.166	-0.221
2. Gender	0.041	-0.309*	-0.282*	-0.121
3. Marital status	0.058	0.290*	0.252	0.188
4. Education	0.,159	0.109	-0.028	-0.053
5. Occupation	-0.140	-0.178	-0.134	-0.048
6. Business ownership	-0.145	0.065	0.218	0.190
7. Position at work	0.144	-0.174	-0.288*	-0.223
8. Length of time at work	0.050	-0.273*	-0.171	-0.126
9. Length of time at work	-0.066	-0.369**	-0.243	-0.059

*0,05

**0,01

A one-way analysis of variance was conducted to determine whether employees' identity and entrepreneurship orientations differed by age. Entrepreneurial orientation did not show any difference across age groups. In terms of identity factors, personal and collective identities differed by age, while social identity did not. In other words, employees in different age groups differed significantly in their views on their personal and social identities. The analysis results are shown in Table 3. The results of the LSD test, conducted to determine which groups the difference existed between, revealed that the personal identity means of those aged 15-25 differed from those aged 51+. Furthermore, according to the LSD test results, the collective identity means of those aged 15-25 differed from those aged 26-35 and 51+. The collective identity means of those aged 36-50 differed only from those aged 51+.

Table 3: One-Way Analysis of Variance Results for Age Variable

		Sum of Squares	d.f.	Mean of Squares	F	p
Personal Identity	Between Groups	4.028	3	1.343	3.962	0.012
	Within Groups	18.981	56	0.339		
	Total	23.010	59			
Collective Identity	Between Groups	3.385	3	1.128	2.986	0.039
	Within Groups	21.160	56	0.378		
	Total	24.545	59			

The results of a t-test conducted to determine whether employees' identity and entrepreneurial orientations differ by gender reveal that personal and social identities differ by gender. Collective identity and entrepreneurial orientation do not differ by gender. The analysis results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Gender Variable t-Test Results

		Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	d.f.	t	p
Personal Identity	Female		25	4,077	0,550	58	2,536	0,014
	Male		35	3,688	0,630			
Social Identity	Female		25	3,068	0,842	58	2,198	0,033
	Male		35	2,604	0,755			

When examining identity and entrepreneurial orientation by marital status, t-test results revealed that only personal identity differed. Neither social nor collective identity, nor entrepreneurial orientation, differed by marital status. The results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Marital Status Variable t-Test Results

		Marital Status	N	Mean	S.D.	d.f.	t	p
Personal Identity	Married		33	3.723	0.544	56	-2.271	0.027
	Single		25	4.081	0.656			

The t-test results, conducted to measure whether identity and entrepreneurial orientation differed based on whether the employee was a boss or a personnel at the workplace, revealed that only social identity differed. Personal and collective identity, as

well as entrepreneurial orientation, did not differ based on whether the employee was a boss or a personnel. The results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: t-Test Results for Being a Boss or Staff

	Employee	N	Mean	S.D.	d.f.	t	p
Social Identity	Personnel	36	3.00	0.781	57	2.269	0.027
	Boss	23	2.52	0.814			

The results of the analysis of variance conducted to determine whether identity and entrepreneurial orientation differed based on tenure in the current job revealed that the difference was only in personal identity. Neither social and collective identity nor entrepreneurial orientation differed based on tenure in the current job. Table 7 shows the results. An LSD test was conducted to determine which groups exhibited the difference. The analysis revealed that the mean personal identity of those who had been employed for 26+ years differed from all other groups.

Table 7: Results of Variance Analysis According to Working Time at Work

		Sum of Squares	d.f.	Mean of Squares	F	p
Personal Identity	Between Groups	4.235	5	0.847	2.517	0.041
	Within Groups	17.835	53	0.337		
	Total	22.069	58			

A variance analysis was conducted to determine whether identity and entrepreneurial orientation differed based on length of employment at the current workplace. The analysis results revealed that personal identity differed. Neither social and collective identity nor entrepreneurial orientation differed based on length of employment at the same workplace. Table 8 displays the analysis results. An LSD test, conducted to determine which groups exhibited the difference, revealed a difference in the average personal identity of those who had worked at their current workplace for 26+ years.

Table 8: Results of Variance Analysis According to Working Hours at the Workplace

		Sum of Squares	d.f.	Mean of Squares	F	p
Personal Identity	Between Groups	5.972	5	1.194	3.933	0.004
	Within Groups	16.097	53	0.304		
	Total	22.069	58			

Multiple regression analysis was conducted to reveal the impact of demographic factors on identity and entrepreneurship. However, the multiple regression results were not statistically significant. This result suggests that the demographic factors identified within the scope of the study had no impact on employees' identity and entrepreneurship orientation.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The research results revealed that employees aged 15-25 have higher personal identity averages than those aged 51+. Similarly, the results show that employees aged 15-25 have higher collective identity averages than those aged 26-35 and 51+. Those aged 36-50 also have higher collective identity averages than those aged 51+. It can be said that

younger employees have higher personal and collective identity averages than older age groups.

The analysis results reveal that female employees have higher personal identity averages than males in terms of both personal and social identity factors. On the other hand, single employees have higher personal identity averages than married employees. Employees working at the workplace have higher social identity averages than those working as bosses. Those who have been in their current job for 26+ years have lower personal identity averages than all other groups. Similarly, the results also show that those who have been in the same job for 26+ years have lower personal identity averages than other groups. Among the findings, entrepreneurial orientation did not differ by age, gender, marital status, education level, line of work, working as a boss or employee, or length of employment at work or workplace. Personal identity did not differ by education level, line of work, or working as a boss or employee, but did differ across other factors. Social identity showed no difference except for gender and working as a boss or employee. Collective identity differed only by age and did not differ across any other factors. The results of the multiple regression analysis conducted to determine the impact of demographic factors on identity and entrepreneurship were not found to be statistically significant.

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